

Breeding success of Black Drongo (*Dicrurus macrocercus*) at Tal Chhapar Black buck sanctuary, Churu (Rajasthan), India

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Abstract

At the Tal Chhapar Sanctuary, a one-year study on Black Drongo breeding activities was conducted from April 2023 to August of 2023. At the studied area, Black Drongo's breeding season ran from May to August. Detailed observations were done on ten Black Drongo nests about the breeding parameters and features of the eggs. A clutch could contain between two and four eggs. The incubation period was 14 days on average. The Black Drongo's successful hatching and fledging was observed. The information acquired on the breeding biology of the Black Drongo could encourage efforts to conserve this species within the field of agriculture.

Keywords Breeding success, Black Drongo, Tal Chhapar, Churu, Rajasthan.

Introduction

In order to determine the condition of habitats within an agro ecosystem, birds serve as crucial ecological indicators (Joshi 2015). Because of anthropogenic factors and habitat destruction, bird populations are declining (Grewal 2000). An important group in the avian biodiversity of agricultural areas is comprised of insectivorous bird species (Dhindsa and Saini 1994). The majority of birds monitor the emergence of insect pest species and hunt their food in the agro-ecosystem (Mariappn *et al.*, 2013). Since they are the most prone to disturbances in agricultural fields, avian insectivorous bird species serve as important indicators of changes in agricultural ecosystems (Okosodo *et al.*, 2016). In the agricultural field areas, they serve as crucial bio-indicators (Powell *et al.*, 2015). The greatest threat to birds is posed by changes in agricultural practices, which can also result in habitat loss, a serious threat to biodiversity. Small terrestrial insectivorous birds, such as the Black Drongo (*Dicrurus macrocercus*), are an important part of the agro-ecosystem (Gomes *et al.*, 2008). Its tail is clearly forked, and it is a member of the Dicruridae family (Ali 2003). In the tree's forked branch, it constructs a delicate nest made of tiny twigs and fibres that resembles a cup (Ali 2002).

Aim of study

The goal of the current study was to observe breeding biology of Black Drongo in Tal Chhapar Black buck Sanctuary, Churu agricultural landscape.

Review of Literature

Black Drongo is a fairly terrestrial bird that perches near the ground in grasslands and cultivations, Okosodo *et al.*, (2016). Black Drongo relative abundance was reported by Kaur *et al.*, (2018) to range from 1.73% to 4.38% in and around village ponds in Punjab's Barnala district. Black Drongo was reported by Sidhu and Kler (2018) to be a less common bird species in orchards, primarily found close to crop fields.

Main Text

Study area

The study was conducted at Tal chhapar sanctuary, situated at the intersection of 27° 42' N and 74° 20' E in the Sujangarh tehsil of district Churu. The sanctuary is home to "the black buck," one of the most graceful antelopes found in India. With its nearly level terrain and sporadic shallow low-lying regions, the Tal Chhapar Sanctuary resembles a typical Savannah thanks to its open grasslands and strewn Acacia trees. "Tal" signifies to "plane land." Rainwater gathers in small seasonal water ponds after flowing through low-lying, shallow areas. It is situated in the path taken by numerous migratory birds,

including harriers. In September, these birds travel through this region. The eastern imperial eagle, tawny eagle, short-toed eagle, sparrow, little green bee-eaters, black ibis, and demoiselle cranes are among the birds that are frequently spotted in the sanctuary. These birds remain there until the month of March. However, throughout the year, one can see ring doves, brown doves, skylarks, crested larks, black drongos and blue jays (Ojha 2016). The climate is very hot (45-50⁰c) in the summer and very cold (4⁰c) in winter and rainfall mainly in June to September. Black Drongo is found in large amount and a residential bird species at study area.